

pos1168 (p=0.04)

pos207 (p=0.026)

pos245 (p=0.024)

pos175 (p=0.018)

pos726 (p=0.019)

pos171 (p=0.022)

pos441 (p=0.01)

pos1046 (p=0.021)

pos266 (p=0.014)

pos170 (p=0.026)

pos537 (p=0.02)

pos121 (p=0.024)

pos1075 (p=0.03)

pos1147 (p=0.029)

pos477 (p=0.023)

pos102 (p=0.037)

pos324 (p=0.017)

pos1061 (p=0.027)

pos568 (p=0.022)

pos296 (p=0.018)

pos180 (p=0.036)

pos99 (p=0.037)

pos75 (p=0.021)

pos697 (p=0.012)

pos588 (p=0.042)

pos285 (p=0.024)

pos1054 (p=0.013)

pos328 (p=0.016)

pos865 (p=0.026)

pos361 (p=0.021)

pos513 (p=0.016)

pos927 (p=0.021)

pos928 (p=0.015)

pos887 (p=0.039)

pos719 (p=0.019)

pos820 (p=0.019)

pos1148 (p=0.018)

pos1035 (p=0.018)

pos1064 (p=0.038)

pos1033 (p=0.037)

pos1037 (p=0.049)

pos1109 (p=0.056)

neg5 (p=-0.005)

neg446 (p=-0.002)

neg553 (p=0.038)

neg436 (p=0.023)

neg540 (p=0.015)

neg407 (p=0.017)

neg207 (p=0.014)

neg336 (p=0.011)

neg291 (p=0.015)

neg176 (p=0.011)

neg311 (p=-0.005)

neg386 (p=0.028)

neg441 (p=-0.005)

